

DMP for Use case BWK

Version : v2 - 26/08/2024

This Data Management Plan aims to provide a brief description of the model and datasets associated with use case BWK.

DMP Authors/Contacts

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Main stakeholder: INBO (Steven De Saeger)

DMP Language

English

1 Brief description of the use case

The Biological valuation map (BVM) is a uniform map of land cover and vegetation types in Flanders, based on fieldwork. The land cover and vegetation types are defined in an extensive list of mapping units. It serves as a reference map for open spaces for anyone involved in nature conservation, spatial planning, environmental reporting, and landscape design in Flanders. The update of the BVM for the entire Flemish region is included in the policy note 2019-2024 by the Flemish Minister for Environment, Zuhal Demir. This goal has been translated into a horizontal project in the Strategic Multi-Year Planning of INBO. The goal of this use case is to perform a pixel classification (semantic segmentation) of the entire Flemish region into BVM mapping units (or higher hierarchical levels).

1.1 What needs to be monitored?

The land use labels of each 10m by 10m land piece of Flanders. This includes distinguishing between various land cover types:

- Beaches and dunes
- Arable land and horticulture
- Grasslands
- Heaths
- Marshes
- Marine biotopes
- Tall herb and pioneer vegetation
- Small landscape elements - undetermined
- Small landscape elements - grassy
- Small landscape elements - woody
- Built-up areas
- Waters
- Forests and shrublands
- Unknown

1.2 Where should it be monitored?

Flanders

1.3 How often should it be monitored?

Every year in the optimal case, at least every three years if possible.

2 Modeling approach

2.1 What type of deep learning problem?

Semantic Segmentation: Labels each pixel in the image (including background) with different colours based on their category class of class label

2.2 Which model type(s) were used?

A vanilla U-Net with a VGG16 encoder backbone (pre-trained on ImageNet).

Future Consideration: Transformers and more complex CNN architectures to better exploit hyperspectral scaling laws.

3 Data

3.1 Description of the input data

The primary input is the TERRASCOPE_S2_TOC_V2 collection, providing Sentinel-2A Top-of-Canopy reflectance data via the OpenEO backend. The workflow utilizes 11 spectral bands, including the Near-Infrared (NIR) band for enhanced vegetation and soil differentiation, all resampled to a consistent 10m spatial resolution. These data cubes are filtered spatially (Flanders region) and temporally (e.g., across the year 2022) to account for seasonal variations. Additionally, the Scene Classification Layer (SCL) is used to mask out cloudy pixels.

3.2 Description of the output data

3.2.1 Dataset 1

Dataset name or title: BWK_biotoopgroep_Sxxx_Syyy_2023-MM-DD

xxx and yyy refer to the geographical subdivision into three subsections: S001-S057, S058-S126 and S127-S194.

MM-DD are the month and day of the predictions, they are set standard to 01-01.

Dataset abstract:

This dataset provides high-resolution (20m) raster layers characterizing the BWK ecotope for 2023 in Flanders, Belgium. Developed within the framework of the GEO.INFORMED project, the data supports the monitoring of European Union greening measures and regional environmental regulations.

Dataset locator: on INBO Google Drive under PRJ_GEO.INFORMED > Research & collaboration > Outputs > Processed outputs > Biologische waarderingskaart > *DATE* >

Resource language: Dutch

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

matthew.blaschko@kuleuven.be

<https://geo-informed.be/>

Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

matthew.blaschko@kuleuven.be

Data format: .tif (geotiff)

Geometry: Raster

Coordinate reference system (CRS): EPSG:3857 - WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator

Geographic bounding box (WGS84): outline of Flanders

Temporal extent: 2023

Date of last revision: 30/09/2024

Lineage: Derived from Sentinel-2 images with a UDF described in the associated workflow documentation.

Bands: 8 bands with prediction probability, one for each BWK class : Strand en duinen (band1), Akkers en tuinbouw (band2), Graslanden (band3), Heiden (band4) Moerassen (band5), Marine biotopen (band6), Ruigten en pioniersvegetatie (band7), Kleine landschapselementen - onbepaald (band8), Kleine landschapselementen - grazig (band9) Kleine landschapselementen -houtig (band10), Bebouwd (band11), Wateren (band12), Bossen en struwelen (band13), Onbekend (band14).

Quality flags: none

Size of the dataset: 8GB

Accessibility: Available on request from Mingshi Li and Matthew Blaschko

Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any): Cannot be made publicly available due to privacy regulations

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Output rasters are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) 'PRJ_GEO.INFORMED' and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files? No

3.3 Description of the reference data

The original format of reference data is in the form of geo-polygons, later rasterized into pixel-wise labels, and is mainly derived from the Biological Valuation map, version 2020. This dataset was overlaid with the LPIS (Land Parcel Identification System) dataset v2019 - known in Flanders as *Landbouwgebruikspcelen*¹ and the Water Surfaces dataset v1.1-2020 - known in Flanders as *Watervlakken*².

3.3.1 Dataset 1

Dataset name or title: Biologische waarderingskaart

¹ <https://metadata.vlaanderen.be/srv/api/records/b70b7280-40a9-4d48-8ecc-c1d9b99808f8>

² https://purews.inbo.be/ws/portalfiles/portal/19271110/Leyssen_etal_2020_WatervlakkenVersie1_1.pdf

Dataset abstract:

The Biological Valuation Map (BWK) is a uniform inventory and evaluation of the entire Flemish territory based on a set of mapping units that represent vegetation, land use and small landscape elements (linear and point-shaped elements). The presence of important fauna elements has also been taken into account. The field inventories for this version of the Biological Valuation Map have been carried out since 1998. The maps have been digitalised and merged into a vector polygon dataset for Flanders.

Dataset locator:

<https://www.vlaanderen.be/datavindplaats/catalogus/biologische-waarderingskaart-en-natura-2000-habitatkaart-toestand-2020>

Resource language: Dutch

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

Steven De Saeger : steven.desaeger@inbo.be

Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

Steven De Saeger : steven.desaeger@inbo.be

Data format: .shp

Geometry: polygons

Coordinate reference system (CRS): Belgian Lambert 72

Geographic bounding box:

westBoundLongitude: 2.541

eastBoundLongitude: 5.907

southBoundLatitude: 50.741

northBoundLatitude: 51.505

Temporal extent: from pre-1998 to 2020

Date of last revision: 2020

Lineage: more information here: <https://publicaties.vlaanderen.be/view-file/67768>

Attributes: more information here: <https://publicaties.vlaanderen.be/view-file/67768>

Quality flags (if available): none

Number of samples in the dataset: 646588 polygons

Size of the dataset (MB): 162 MB

Screenshot of attribute table:

	TAG	VAL	EENH1	EENH2	EENH3	EENH4	EENH5	EENH6	EENH7	EENH8	SHAPE_Leng	SHAPE_Area	Biotope_1	Biotope_2t	Year	Label
1	00001_v2020	m	ad	NULL	393.14819410700	9372.48281540000	Urban areas	Towns, villages ...	2002	12						
2	00002_v2020	mw	ad	ku	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	307.42626768000	4490.66278208000	Urban areas	Towns, villages ...	old	12
3	00003_v2020	m	ad	NULL	224.03083282900	2895.39502250000	Urban areas	Towns, villages ...	1998	12						
4	00004_v2020	m	ad	NULL	504.59296340900	4333.22083203900	Urban areas	Towns, villages ...	1998	12						
5	00005_v2020	m	ad	NULL	447.47074201500	11515.157682900	Urban areas	Towns, villages ...	old	12						
6	00006_v2020	m	aer-	NULL	110.73878632300	612.10746953200	Water bodies	Surface standin...	2005	13						
7	00007_v2020	m	aer-	NULL	71.04853258580	312.86300523300	Water bodies	Surface standin...	2005	13						
8	00008_v2020	m	aer-	NULL	97.42610010650	591.35408742800	Water bodies	Surface standin...	2005	13						
9	00009_v2020	m	aer-	NULL	136.44789450600	1063.65238435000	Water bodies	Surface standin...	2005	13						
10	00010_v2020	m	aer-	NULL	343.45531926200	8012.61633928000	Water bodies	Surface standin...	2005	13						
11	00011_v2020	m	aer-	NULL	196.51508347100	1666.11014196000	Water bodies	Surface standin...	2005	13						
12	00012_v2020	m	aer-	NULL	99.08863513470	676.79748036800	Water bodies	Surface standin...	2005	13						
13	00013_v2020	m	aer-	NULL	109.31058280000	531.09217666400	Water bodies	Surface standin...	2005	13						
14	00014_v2020	m	aer-	NULL	78.22428274690	350.27211619400	Water bodies	Surface standin...	2005	13						
15	00015_v2020	m	aer-	NULL	220.41685791400	2411.18784427000	Water bodies	Surface standin...	2005	13						
16	00016_v2020	m	aer-	NULL	133.40879162300	1118.02420042000	Water bodies	Surface standin...	2005	13						
17	00017_v2020	m	aer-	NULL	145.51721431300	1109.55126464000	Water bodies	Surface standin...	2005	13						
18	00018_v2020	m	aer-	NULL	197.05704564300	2280.79765003000	Water bodies	Surface standin...	2005	13						

Screenshot of geometry (subpart):

Accessibility: public dataset

Restrictions on making the data publicly available: none

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Reference data are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) PRJ_GEO.INFORMED and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files?

No